

N¹-(Morpholino/Pyrrolidino/Piperidino Thiocarbonyl Thioacetyl)-N³-Substituted Phenyl Carbamides

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Twentyseven N¹-(morpholino/pyrrolidino/piperidino thiocarbonyl thioacetyl)-N³-substituted phenyl carbamides have been prepared and screened for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium equiseti* and *Drechlera papendorfii*. Only two compounds, viz. N¹-(morpholinothiocabonyl thioacetyl)-N³-*o*-chlorophenyl carbamide and N¹-(morpholinothiocabonyl thioacetyl)-N³-*p*-iodophenyl carbamide were found to possess significant antifungal activity.

A large number of dithiocarbamates¹ have been known to be potent fungicides. Recently Sen Gupta *et al* have reported the synthesis and insecticidal activity of several new dithiocarbamates². The ability of some halogenonitrophenyl and naphthyl esters of piperidino and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids³ to exhibit fungicidal activity prompted us to synthesise the title compounds. These were also evaluated for their antifungal activity.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and were not corrected.

Aryl carbamides and their corresponding chloroacetyl derivatives were prepared according to the

methods reported earlier^{4,5,6}. Ammonium substituted-N-carbodithioates⁷ were prepared from morpholine, pyrrolidine and piperidine.

N¹-(Morpholino/pyrrolidino/piperidinothiocarbonyl thioacetyl)-N³-substituted phenyl carbamides

A solution of ammonium substituted-N-carbodithioates (0.01 mole) in 20 ml of acetone was added to a suspension of appropriate chloroacetyl-N-substituted phenyl carbamides (0.01 mole) in 30 ml of acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr and then refluxed for 2 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid which separated out on cooling was filtered, washed several times with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF N¹-(MORPHOLINO/PYRROLIDINO/PIPERIDINO THIOCARBONYL THIOACETYL)-N³-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL CARBAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	H	82	178	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	11.98	12.39
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	81	206	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	11.50	11.89
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	73	175	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	11.52	11.89
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	76	200	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	11.49	11.89
5.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	71	172	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	11.20	11.38
6.	<i>o</i> -Cl	82	210	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃ Cl	11.00	11.21
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl	86	179	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃ Cl	11.12	11.21
8.	<i>p</i> -Br	80	209	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃ Br	9.52	10.04
9.	<i>p</i> -I	84	182	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃ I	9.00	9.03

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(Table 1 Contd.)

10.	H	87	168	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	12.00	12.46
11.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	82	159	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	11.41	11.94
12.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	74	115	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	11.43	11.94
13.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	76	198	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	11.46	11.94
14.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	75	99	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	11.32	11.44
15.	<i>o</i> -Cl	82	171	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.91	11.31
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	84	142	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	10.83	11.31
17.	<i>p</i> -Br	79	170	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Br	9.79	10.09
18.	<i>p</i> -I	81	177	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ I	8.73	9.07

19.	H	83	189	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	12.60	13.00
20.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	80	194	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	12.02	12.46
21.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	74	125	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	12.04	12.46
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	78	198	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	12.07	12.46
23.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	79	174	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	11.63	11.89
24.	<i>o</i> -Cl	81	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	11.23	11.75
25.	<i>p</i> -Cl	79	197	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	11.30	11.75
26.	<i>p</i> -Br	83	172	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ Br	9.89	10.45
27.	<i>p</i> -I	81	155	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ I	8.99	9.35

Screening Results

Compounds listed in Table 1 were screened *in vitro* for their antifungal activity against the fungi *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium equiseti* and *Drechslera papendorfii* by "Paper-Disc Plate method"⁸ at concentrations of 2%, 0.2%, 0.02% and 0.002% (W/V). The

solutions of these concentrations were prepared by dissolving the compounds in acetone. Control was taken of pure acetone. Filter paper discs of 12 mm diameter were used. The zones of inhibition at each concentration were measured and are recorded in Table 2. No zone of inhibition was observed in control. It is evident from the table that out of

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF N¹-(MORPHOLINO/PYRROLIDINO/PIPERIDINO THIOCARBONYL THIOACETYL)-N⁸-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL CARBAMIDES

* Compd. No.	Diameter of zones of inhibition in mm for pathogenic fungi at concentrations											
	<i>Fusarium equiseti</i>				<i>Alternaria alternata</i>				<i>Drechslera papendorfii</i>			
	2%	0.2%	0.02%	0.002%	2%	0.2%	0.02%	0.002%	2%	0.2%	0.02%	0.002%
1.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	15	—	—	—
2.	17	—	—	—	16	—	—	—	18	14	—	—
3.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.	—	—	—	—	17	14	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	21.5	16	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6.	28	20	17	15	30	20	16	15	32	25	20	18
7.	25	17	—	—	30	15	—	—	30	21	17	—
8.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	30	25	19	14	28	19	16	14	32	24	22	18
10.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
11.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
12.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
13.	—	—	—	—	20	15	—	—	25	—	—	—
14.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
15.	—	—	—	—	15	—	—	—	16	14	—	—
16.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
17.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
18.	—	—	—	—	16	14.5	—	—	18	15.5	—	—
19.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
20.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
21.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
22.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
23.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
24.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	15	—	—	—
25.	—	—	—	—	15	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
26.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
27.	17	14.5	—	—	19	14	—	—	21	16.5	—	—

* Compound Nos. correspond to S. Nos. of the compounds in Table 1.

(-) Shows no zone of inhibition.

twentyseven compounds studied, compounds numbered 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 13, 15, 18, 24, 25 and 27 possess antifungal activity. Compounds numbered 6 and 9 having *o*-Cl and *p*-I as the R substituents were found to have greater inhibition against all the three fungi at all the four concentrations. Compounds numbered 2 and 7 possessing *o*-CH₃ and *p*-Cl as the R substituents of morpholine-N-carbodithioates and compound numbered 27 possessing *p*-I as the R substituent are also active against all the three fungi but at higher concentrations. In the present study, it appears that the significant antifungal activity is associated with carbamides containing morpholine moiety.

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